

Nore, H. & Lahn, L.C. (2019). How can apprentices learn and develop professional competences through ePortfolios? In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.171-175) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641862>

How can apprentices learn and develop professional competences through ePortfolios?

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Abstract

Work-based learning is an important part of vocational education and training in many countries. As such, trainers have responsibilities that go beyond instruction and include learning support and feedback, as apprentices need to reflect on their professional development and responsibilities. Different kinds of ePortfolios are designed to support learners and trainers in developmental processes, promote knowledge sharing and underpin transferable skills as part of a professional competence. In this paper, we will discuss the impact of different designs: developmental, accounting, assessment and management tools. We will link the discussion to the underlying understandings of what is competence or professional competence in the different types of tools. Finally, we will look into the learning potential in ePortfolios.

Keywords

ePortfolio; innovative apprenticeship; transferable skills; professional competence

1 Introduction

There is an increasing use of ePortfolios, both in higher professional education (van der Schaaf, 2019) and in vocational education (Schwendimann et al., 2015), brought in as innovative ways of linking work and learning (Attwell & Pumilia, 2007). Even though our study is from a Norwegian context, the discussions on how authentic experiences combined with reflections, mediation of meaning and a deeper understanding of work processes and learning to learn are universal (Elsholz & Knutzen, 2010; Billett, 2014).

The paper is based on data from a former study on quality in VET where we interviewed apprentices, in-company trainers and training offices and used documentary evidence from e-portfolios, local training plans, task descriptions, assignments and assessment schemes for validation and elaboration (Lahn & Nore, 2018).

In this paper, we will first introduce the Norwegian context for learning through apprenticeship, then the use of ePortfolios, followed by contrasting understandings of vocational and professional competence. The final discussion reflects two research questions: What kind of learning processes take place when apprentices and trainers use different types of ePortfolios? In what ways do apprentices learn to be professionals by using ePortfolios?

2 Hybrid learning arenas in Norwegian VET

In vocational education and training (VET), students and apprentices learn in different contexts: partly in schools, partly in training enterprises and partly through digital media. The amount of learning in each arena differs from country to country. For example, in Norway we have a sequential dual model with two years in VET schools, followed by two years of ap-

prenticeship in enterprises. In addition, a work-based subject is added for the school-based part, which means that approximately 1/3 of the vocational schooling in the first two years is work-based in enterprises. When entering apprenticeship, approximately 80% of the apprentices sign a training contract with a training office on the one hand, and a work contract with an enterprise on the other. The training offices hold the responsibility for the training according to state regulated curricula and quality standards set by the owners of the training offices, which are the training enterprises. The training enterprises hold the responsibility for the instructions and follow-up of apprentices in daily work. Training offices offers consultancy and support to the enterprises and apprentices and build bridges to vocational schools. To this complex field, we add an institutional dimension by positioning the ePortfolio systems as a liaison device between apprentices, training offices, schools and enterprises that forms a kind of hybrid learning arena (Lahn & Nore, 2018). The ePortfolios are often regarded as a crucial part of the training offices' quality systems.

After the two years in VET schools, teachers no longer have responsibility for the learners. In the companies, apprentices have one or more trainers, lots of colleagues and often co-apprentices to discuss with on the quality of performed work. This means trainers have responsibilities that go beyond instruction and include learning support and feedback. The training offices are not available for apprentices in their daily work and cannot encourage the apprentices directly to reflect on their professional development and responsibilities, but do look at the possibilities of using ePortfolios, both as a substitute and to support learning processes.

3 ePortfolios

The use of ePortfolios is often mentioned as a tool for supporting professional development in-between learning arenas (Ortoleva & Betrancourt, 2015; Schwendimann et al., 2015; Nore & Lahn, 2014). In addition, ePortfolios give teachers and trainers opportunities to try out a tailor-made education, and to reflect on learning strategies and their impact (Nore, 2015).

International studies show how the use of ePortfolios in vocational education and training promote interaction between schools and businesses (Mauroux et al., 2016). ePortfolios may contribute to knowledge sharing between apprentices and strengthen their basic skills, including digital competence and the ability to learn to learn. These skills are commonly referred to as "21st century skills", core work skills (Brewer, 2013) or transferable skills (Nägele & Stalder, 2017).

Findings from our study show that ePortfolios are used very differently across vocations and training offices. This also goes for their ability to mediate or integrate between the different institutions and actors in the dual model, as well as between apprentices as peer learning. The variations in learning activities and the use of ePortfolios represent historical differences among trades. Plumbers, industrial mechanics and automation bear long traditions of apprenticeship and performance-based assessments and as such on the documentation of performed work, reflections on the quality of work and the development of professional identity. Sales and health care are newcomers in Norwegian VET, and struggle with the apprenticeship system. In these trades, we found ePortfolios used in a more scholastic oriented way, with fixed and written assignments assessed by the training offices.

Formerly (Lahn & Nore, 2018), we have discussed the use of ePortfolios in Norwegian VET along four lines: (1) *Developmental ePortfolios*, which enable an understanding of personal progression in competence development; (2) *ePortfolios as accounting devices* which support training companies and training offices in their statutory obligation to report to regional authorities; (3) *ePortfolios as assessment tools*, in which apprentices may compare their skills and competences with the national curricula on the one side, and the in-company standards on the other; and (4) *Learning management through ePortfolios* - Standard assignments that prevent the apprentices from using authentic tasks as objects of reflection.

We concluded that ePortfolios mainly support restrictive learning processes and indicated improvement, particularly for networked learning and explicating tacit knowledge. More innovative feedback and assessment procedures could be linked to the recognition of apprentices socializing, working and learning online, thereby challenging established boundaries for learning in both time and space (Brown et al., 1989; Brown, 2008).

In our study, we found that trainers and peers were rarely connected to the apprentices' ePortfolios, whereas the main communication was between the apprentices and the training office. In the following, we want to pursue the question of whether this is due to the designs of ePortfolios, with underlying differences in the understanding of what is professional competence and how such competence can be developed, as supported by ePortfolios.

4 Professional Competence

According to Mulder (2014), professional competence consist of domain-specific activities, which can be demonstrated through individuals' performances, and professionals are competent when they act responsibly and effectively according to given standards of performance. Such standards are either competence-oriented or competence-based frameworks (Mulder, 2017). Learning outcomes as described in Norwegian vocational curricula are competence-oriented, and in accordance with European Qualification Frameworks (EQF). They describe intended learning without any guidelines for the organization of learning processes. Trainers, and colleagues at the workplace, do not necessarily understand how to convert learning outcomes into relevant work tasks and learning processes, and leave the interpretations to the training offices.

In contrast, competence-based frameworks identify core occupational tasks with defined competences, and act as roadmaps for competence development (Mulder, 2017). This may also link to the German concept of Lernfelder, and the influence on the German curriculum development (see Gessler, 2017). Such frameworks are easy to identify for training establishments, but may be either too functional (no generic competences), too restricted (no transversal or transferable skills) or too situational (restricted to a company-specific context and culture).

Learning to be professional goes through immediate responses to experiences at work. Trainers, peers and customers provide feedback to apprentices every day as part of an authentic assessment (Gulikers et al., 2004), but rarely in ePortfolios. Apprentices construe and construct from a broad range of experiences with work tasks, problem solving, customer claims, deviances, cooperation, etc. The brute and social mediating factors through work experiences help shape the personal development process for those who think, act and learn. Through reflections and negotiations, apprentices build their own domain-specific professional conceptions, procedures and values (Billett, 2017).

Vocational curricula in Norway are developed in cooperation with actors representing the various vocational domains, serving as a common competence standard for trade or journeyman's certificates and form the basis for work-based training. This is why the curricular (competence-oriented) learning outcomes are central elements in most ePortfolios.

5 Discussion

In our study, there were just a few ePortfolios that could be named as developmental tools to support apprentices' meaning making on authentic work tasks, and to build professional identity in a broad sense. It seems as if ePortfolios serve more as quality assurance for learning and development according to standardized learning outcomes. Here, the training office plays a major role, and the apprentice fills in schemes just ahead of obligatory half-year reviews.

This is part of statutory reports to the regional educational authorities, but does not serve as a tool for developing professional competence and pride.

The primary actors in the learning processes should be the individual apprentices, as their learning and reflections are close to the core work tasks at the specific workplace supported by feedback from local trainers, co-workers, peer-apprentices and management. If trainers and peers should engage in the process, they need to be involved in the identification of core work task and processes with defined competences. When they recognize the descriptions and requirements, it is easier to give feedback and involve in developmental processes. Where ePortfolios are closer to company-specific descriptions and requirements, trainers seem to be more involved and apprentices appreciate and utilize the tool.

In addition to core work tasks and competence requirements, ePortfolios should be designed for more actors; apprentices, peer-apprentices, trainers, colleagues, training offices and perhaps teachers. Situational learning is collaborative and includes common reflections and negotiations on, for instance, responsibilities and autonomy at work, work process learning, problem solving and innovations.

We have introduced ePortfolios as hybrid learning arenas linking the different VET actors together, and preparing the basis for more collaborative learning and perspective making. A redesign of ePortfolios from a strict curriculum design or a simple task-oriented design is needed to make them more interactive, collaborative, and opening up for both meaning making and perspective making. According to Billett (2014), meaning making is the most central and enduring way in which occupational knowledge is learned, sustained and remade. Another part of learning to become professionals is perspective making, a process of becoming aware of one's own perspectives in relation to the perspectives of others, and of learning to look at one's own practices through the eyes of others (Bakker & Akkerman, 2017). We are looking forward to studying the effect on learning to be professionals from redesigned ePortfolios that are more collaborative and open to continuous development and negotiations of professional competences, including transferable skills.

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